

remaining N was topdressed in two equal splits at tillering and at panicle initiation. Two seedlings/hill were transplanted at 25- × 15-cm spacing.

The highest grain yield (6.2 t/ha) was with 30 Nov seeding and transplanting

55-d-old seedlings (see table). The lowest yield (3.3 t/ha) was with seeding on 15 Dec and transplanting 65-d-old seedlings.

In general, early seeding gave higher yields with older seedlings and late

seeding gave higher yields with younger seedlings. Low temperature during early seeding dates restricted seedling growth. Transplanting young seedlings during cold days hindered crop establishment. □

Scarifying seeds of green manure legumes

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The hard seededness characteristic of green manure legume seeds often

prevents germination, leading to poor stands. We studied scarification methods appropriate for a low technology production program.

Seeds of *Aeschynomena uniflora*, *A. schimperii*, *A. sensitiva*, *Sesbania rostrata*, and an unidentified *Sesbania* species were harvested in Jun. In Oct, 3 scarification methods were applied: concentrated H₂SO₄ from 0 to 180 min, boiling water from 0 to 90 min, and abrasion with sand. Seeds (20/ treatment replicated twice) were germinated on moist filter paper at 30 °C.

Acid and mechanical abrasion

1. Germination of green manure legume seeds by time of scarification with concentrated H₂SO₄. Madagascar, 1986.

2. Germination of green manure by legume seeds scarified by abrasion with sand. Madagascar, 1986.

methods of scarification were effective, but boiling water was not. Germination of H₂SO₄-treated seed varied by species (Fig. 1). The highest germination of sesbania was achieved with seeds soaked in H₂SO₄ for 2 h.

Mechanical abrasion was effective for *A. uniflora* but not for *A. schimperii* or *A. sensitiva*. Mechanical abrasion of sesbania seeds increased germination 45% (Fig. 2). □

Whole-plant ratooning technique

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With traditional ratooning techniques, yields are low, 20-30% of the main crop yield. Lack of adequate leaf area may be a factor in the lower ratoon yields. We tried using mother leaves for the ratoon